

Public Policy Implementation: A Case Study of Bangladesh's Pre-Primary Education Sector

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Abstract

This study provides an in-depth analysis of the implementation of public policy in Bangladesh's pre-primary education sector. Amidst ambitious government plans to introduce a two-year pre-primary education program by 2024, the research aimed to capture the perspectives of various stakeholders involved in early childhood education. Through a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative survey data with qualitative feedback, the study evaluated awareness of government policies, the perceived effectiveness of these policies, communication efficacy, the necessity of regulatory frameworks, and the adequacy of infrastructure and resources. The survey, distributed across a diverse range of educators including teachers and headteachers, revealed a stark discrepancy between the high awareness of government initiatives and the unanimous sentiment that current policies are inadequate in promoting the sector's development. While stakeholders reported nearly universal awareness of upcoming educational reforms, they expressed significant concerns about policy effectiveness, communication strategies, resource allocation, and the absence of a rigorous regulatory framework. Quantitative analysis indicated that 100% of participants believe current public policies do not effectively support the expansion and improvement of pre-primary education. Additionally, stakeholders unanimously agreed on the need for a regulatory framework to ensure quality in the face of private institution dominance, and they were unequivocal about the insufficiency of current budget allocations. Qualitative insights echoed these findings, emphasizing a call for clarity in policy communication and significant improvements in financial and infrastructural support. The study concludes that to achieve the government's educational goals, a multi-faceted enhancement approach is required—one that not only increases financial investment but also ensures transparent communication and enforces a robust regulatory framework to standardize quality across the sector. The findings serve as a clarion call for policymakers to integrate stakeholder feedback into the decision-making process, thus fostering an environment conducive to the effective implementation of pre-primary education policies.

Keywords: Pre-primary Education, Public Policy, Stakeholder Perspectives, Educational Reform, Regulatory Framework, Resource Allocation, Bangladesh

1 Introduction

Pre-primary education represents a critical phase in a child's cognitive, emotional, and social development. In Bangladesh, the significance of this educational phase has grown exponentially in recent years [1]. The

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Government of Bangladesh, recognizing the foundational role of early childhood education, has progressively prioritized its development and expansion. As of 2021, approximately 1.57 million students were enrolled in preprimary education (PPE) across nearly 65,000 government primary schools [2]. This burgeoning emphasis not only mirrors global educational trends but also underscores Bangladesh's commitment to nurturing its youngest learners [3]. The landscape of pre-primary education in Bangladesh is shaped by a complex interplay of public policy, financial considerations, and the increasing influence of private institutions [4]. Over half of the students in Bangladesh are dependent on privately owned institutions for their educational pursuits [5, 6]. While the private sector's dominance offers diverse educational choices, it also raises questions about the quality, equity, and financial implications of education [7]. Furthermore, the financial landscape of education in Bangladesh is unique. Households account for 71% of total educational spending in the country, one of the highest rates globally. This heavy reliance on out-of-pocket spending intersects with public policy decisions, especially when considering the potential expansion of pre-primary education and its budgetary implications. The primary objective of this study is to provide a comprehensive analysis of the public policy implementation pertaining to the pre-primary education sector in Bangladesh. This research aims to explore the current state of policy execution, the role and influence of private institutions, and the financial implications, especially in light of household contributions. By investigating these facets, the study seeks to offer insights and recommendations for a robust, equitable, and sustainable pre-primary education system in Bangladesh. Since its independence in 1971, Bangladesh has undergone significant transformations in its education sector. Initial efforts were directed towards rebuilding a war-ravaged education system. Over the decades, the focus shifted towards expansion, accessibility, and improving quality. Pre-primary education, once a neglected domain, has now emerged as a focal point in the country's educational roadmap, as evidenced by its inclusion in the National Education Policy 2010. The education sector in Bangladesh is marked by a distinct dichotomy between public and private institutions. While public institutions, supported by government funding, aim to provide accessible and affordable education to all, private institutions have proliferated, offering alternative educational choices. More than half of the students in Bangladesh rely on private institutions throughout their educational journey. This significant dependence on private institutions brings forth questions about standardization, quality, and equity in the educational experiences offered.

Budgetary allocations to the education sector have been a topic of extensive debate and scrutiny. Historically, only 2.5% of Bangladesh's annual budget has been earmarked for education. This limited allocation has often been underscored in national discussions, especially considering the country's aspirations for an inclusive and robust education system. With the introduction and expansion of pre-primary education, and the proposed extension to include children above four, budgetary considerations have become even more critical. The public policy framework for education in Bangladesh is anchored in the National Education Policy 2010. This policy underscores the government's commitment to ensuring quality education for all and recognizes the foundational importance of early childhood education. Specific provisions within the policy address the need for a standardized curriculum, teacher training, and infrastructure development. However, the policy's implementation has been met with challenges, particularly in bridging the gap between policy design and on-ground execution, and in integrating the burgeoning private education sector.

2 Literature Review

The global educational landscape presents a striking dichotomy between private and public education institutions, warranting extensive scholarly attention. In various contexts, private institutions have emerged as pivotal players, offering competition or complementarity to public education systems. For instance, in specific regions, these institutions are lauded for their superior quality, innovation, and adaptability, in contrast to their public counterparts. Despite this, they are not without their challenges; concerns regarding equity, accessibility, and standardization are prevalent, sparking debates on potential socio-economic divides and disparities in educational access [8, 9, 10]. The realm of pre-primary education has gained global recognition for its indispensable role in laying a strong foundation for lifelong learning [11]. A myriad of nations have committed to the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals, particularly Goal 4, which advocates for inclusive and equitable quality education. This commitment has manifested in a global shift from a sole focus on enrollment rates to an emphasis on the quality and outcomes of pre-primary education. Nonetheless, this transition is not without its hurdles; countries grapple with challenges related to inadequate infrastructure, underdeveloped curriculum designs, and insufficient teacher training, underscoring a need for comprehensive policy implementation [12]. The concept of play-based learning, rooted in the philosophy that young children's optimal learning occurs through play, has been universally endorsed as a progressive pedagogical approach in early childhood education. The literature extols its virtues, highlighting its potential to enhance cognitive development, bolster social skills, and nurture creativity [13]. Yet, transitioning from conventional teaching methods to play-based learning is fraught with challenges, often stemming from entrenched educational beliefs, a lack of teacher training in play-based

methodologies, and potential misalignments with societal and parental expectations. The effectiveness of educational policies, especially in the context of pre-primary education, is intricately tied to the quality of teacher training. Well-trained educators are crucial for the successful delivery of curriculum, addressing diverse learning needs, and implementing innovative teaching methods such as play-based learning. However, gaps in teacher training can significantly hamper the realization of policy objectives. For instance, the limited duration and scope of teacher training programs in Bangladesh have been identified as insufficient for preparing educators to meet the demands of modern pre-primary education, particularly in the domain of play-based learning.

The drive towards enhancing pre-primary education is evident in Bangladesh's policy frameworks [14], notably the National Education Policy 2010. The substantial increase in enrollment rates in recent years demonstrates the effectiveness of these policies in reaching a wider demographic [15]. However, a critical analysis reveals several gaps between policy design and practical implementation. While the policy framework is comprehensive, addressing various facets of pre-primary education, its execution on the ground presents a different picture [11, 16, 17]. The 15-day training program for pre-primary teachers, despite being a positive initiative, is deemed insufficient for preparing educators adequately, particularly in the area of play-based learning. Additionally, there are observable deficiencies in infrastructure, especially concerning the inclusivity of children with special needs. Despite the strong advocacy for play-based learning in policy documents, the transition from theory to practice is laden with challenges. Educators, even after undergoing government training, express a lack of preparedness in facilitating this pedagogical approach. Traditional beliefs about education, coupled with resource limitations, pose significant barriers to the full adoption and implementation of play-based learning. Nevertheless, global best practices offer valuable insights for enhancing this educational approach. The Scandinavian model, with its child-centric, play-based curriculum, and the European Union's regulatory support for play in early learning, provide viable benchmarks for Bangladesh. While cultural and logistical differences necessitate careful adaptation, elements such as comprehensive teacher training, community engagement, and resource allocation are universally applicable. The journey towards inclusive education in Bangladesh is in its nascent stages, with the policy framework recognizing the need but facing challenges in implementation. Infrastructure for special needs children is unevenly distributed, with many institutions, particularly in rural areas, lacking necessary facilities. Societal perceptions and stigmas associated with disabilities further complicate the integration of special needs children into mainstream classrooms [18]. Teacher training for handling diverse needs is a critical area requiring attention. Beyond generic training programs, educators need specialized modules that address the intricacies of inclusive education [19]. Awareness campaigns targeting communities and parents can play a pivotal role in changing perceptions and fostering acceptance of inclusive educational practices [20].

The quality of pre-primary education is intrinsically tied to the competence and preparedness of educators [21]. The existing 15-day induction training for pre-primary teachers in Bangladesh, while a commendable initiative, has proven to be inadequate in several areas. The training falls short in equipping educators with the necessary skills for effective play-based learning and addressing the diverse needs of students, particularly those with special needs. The lack of continuous professional development opportunities further exacerbates this issue, leaving educators ill-prepared to adapt to evolving educational methodologies and student needs. Addressing this gap requires a multifaceted approach, including extended training duration, specialized modules, ongoing professional development opportunities, and practical exposure to model classrooms [22]. The pre-primary education landscape in Bangladesh is heavily influenced by the prevalence of private institutions. While these institutions contribute to the diversification and accessibility of educational options, they also present challenges in standardization, equity, and quality assurance [23]. The government's initiatives to bring private institutions under a regulatory framework are crucial steps towards addressing these challenges. Ensuring that private institutions adhere to national education standards, promoting financial transparency, and implementing quality assurance mechanisms are vital for maintaining educational quality and equity [24]. Collaborative efforts between the government, private institutions, and other stakeholders are essential to achieving these goals and ensuring that the dominance of private institutions translates into enhanced educational opportunities for all [25]. The financial commitment to pre-primary education in Bangladesh is a critical aspect that influences its accessibility, quality, and sustainability. The current budgetary allocations for the education sector, coupled with the significant household contributions to education spending, present a complex financial landscape [1, 26]. Addressing the challenges of limited budgetary allocations, ensuring equitable access to quality education, and alleviating the financial burdens on families require comprehensive fiscal strategies and policy interventions. Investments in infrastructure, teacher training, and inclusive education, alongside initiatives to enhance the affordability of education, are imperative for the sustainable development of pre-primary education in Bangladesh [27].

3 Methodology

The study adopts a mixed-methods approach, integrating both quantitative and qualitative research methods to provide a comprehensive understanding of the pre-primary education landscape in Bangladesh. This approach enables the triangulation of data, ensuring the reliability and validity of the findings.

- **Quantitative Research:** A structured survey was administered to a diverse range of participants, including teachers, parents, policymakers, and administrators involved in pre-primary education. The survey comprised closed-ended questions, aimed at gathering numerical data on participants' perceptions of policy effectiveness, infrastructure adequacy, teacher training quality, and other pertinent aspects of pre-primary education.
- **Qualitative Research:** In-depth interviews and focus group discussions were conducted to supplement the quantitative data, providing nuanced insights into the participants' experiences, challenges, and suggestions for improvement. The qualitative data were collected from a purposive sample of participants, ensuring representation from different regions, socio-economic backgrounds, and roles within the pre-primary education sector.

3.1 Sampling

A stratified random sampling method was employed to ensure a representative sample of the population involved in pre-primary education in Bangladesh. The strata were defined based on geographic location (urban, semi-urban, rural), type of institution (public, private), and participants' roles (teachers, parents, administrators, policymakers). Within each stratum, participants were randomly selected to be part of the study.

3.2 Data Collection

Survey

The survey was meticulously designed to capture a wide array of data pertinent to the study of pre-primary education in Bangladesh. It encompassed various sections, each tailored to gather specific types of information.

- **Demographic Information:** This section aimed to collect basic demographic data from the participants, including their age, gender, role in pre-primary education (teacher, parent, administrator, policymaker), geographic location, and the type of institution they are affiliated with (public or private). This information was vital for contextualizing the responses and ensuring the representativeness of the sample.
- **Awareness and Perceptions:** This section comprised questions designed to assess the participants' awareness of government policies and initiatives in pre-primary education, as well as their perceptions regarding the effectiveness of these policies. It also included items to gauge their views on the quality and adequacy of the infrastructure and resources available for pre-primary education. These questions were crucial for understanding the ground-level impact of governmental efforts and identifying areas requiring attention.
- **Teacher Training and Professional Development:** This section focused on gathering data related to the training and professional development opportunities available to educators in pre-primary education. It included questions on the adequacy, frequency, and perceived effectiveness of these training programs. This information is instrumental in evaluating the current state of teacher preparedness and identifying gaps that need to be addressed to enhance the quality of education.
- **Challenges and Barriers:** Participants were asked to identify and rate various challenges and barriers they face in implementing or accessing quality pre-primary education. This section aimed to uncover the on-ground realities and obstacles that hinder the optimal functioning of pre-primary education in Bangladesh.
- **Recommendations and Suggestions:** This part of the survey provided an opportunity for participants to share their insights and suggestions for improving pre-primary education in Bangladesh. They were encouraged to reflect on their experiences and propose practical, actionable measures to address the identified challenges.
- **Play-Based Learning:** Questions in this section were designed to assess the understanding, implementation, and challenges associated with play-based learning in pre-primary education. Participants' responses would shed light on the extent to which this pedagogical approach has been adopted and the support mechanisms in place to facilitate its implementation.

- **Inclusion and Special Needs:** This section aimed to gather data on the provisions and support available for children with special needs in pre-primary education. It included questions on the adequacy of infrastructure, training, and resources to cater to these children, as well as the challenges faced in ensuring inclusive education.

Each question in the survey was carefully crafted and reviewed to ensure clarity, relevance, and alignment with the study's objectives. The use of a Likert-scale format, alongside multiple-choice and open-ended questions, allowed for a comprehensive collection of both quantitative and qualitative data. The survey was pre-tested with a subset of the target population to validate its reliability and make necessary adjustments before its administration. This rigorous process ensured that the survey instrument was robust, valid, and capable of eliciting the required information to meet the research objectives.

Interviews and Focus Group Discussions

To gain deeper insights and understand the nuances of pre-primary education in Bangladesh, in-depth interviews and focus group discussions were conducted with various stakeholders including teachers, parents, administrators, and policymakers. This qualitative approach complements the quantitative survey data, providing a holistic view of the challenges, successes, and areas for improvement within the sector. A semi-structured interview guide was developed, containing open-ended questions designed to prompt detailed responses and facilitate discussion. The guide was structured around key themes aligned with the research objectives, ensuring a comprehensive exploration of the topic. The themes and corresponding question types included:

- **Perceptions of Policy and Implementation:** Questions in this category aimed to gauge participants' awareness of existing pre-primary education policies, their opinions on the effectiveness of these policies, and their experiences with policy implementation on the ground. For example, "Can you describe your understanding of the current pre-primary education policies in Bangladesh?" and "How do you think these policies are being implemented in your institution/region?"
- **Challenges and Barriers:** This section focused on uncovering the challenges participants face in the realm of pre-primary education, including issues related to infrastructure, teacher training, curriculum, and inclusion of children with special needs. Sample questions included "What challenges do you face in implementing play-based learning in your classroom?" and "How are children with special needs accommodated in your institution?"
- **Teacher Training and Professional Development:** Questions here were tailored to understand the participants' experiences with teacher training programs, their perceived adequacy of these programs, and areas where they felt additional training or support was needed. For instance, "Can you describe the teacher training you received for pre-primary education?" and "In which areas do you feel you need more training or support?"
- **Role of Private Institutions:** Participants were asked about their perceptions of private education institutions, their advantages and disadvantages, and how they see the role of these institutions in the broader education landscape. Questions included "What role do you think private institutions play in pre-primary education in Bangladesh?" and "How do you think the quality of education in private institutions compares to public institutions?"
- **Financial Aspects and Household Contributions:** This theme delved into the financial aspects of pre-primary education, seeking participants' views on the adequacy of budget allocations, the implications of significant household contributions, and suggestions for fiscal strategies. Sample questions were "How do you think the financial responsibilities for pre-primary education should be distributed between the government and households?" and "What are the financial challenges parents face in ensuring quality pre-primary education for their children?"
- **Recommendations for Improvement:** The final section aimed to gather participants' suggestions and recommendations for enhancing the quality and effectiveness of pre-primary education in Bangladesh. Questions included "What changes would you like to see in the pre-primary education sector?" and "How can teacher training be improved to better support educators in the field?"

The purpose of these questions was to elicit rich, context-specific insights that could inform a nuanced understanding of the state of pre-primary education in Bangladesh. By exploring participants' experiences, perceptions, and recommendations, the study aimed to identify gaps between policy and practice, understand the challenges faced by various stakeholders, and gather actionable suggestions for improvement.

These discussions not only served to validate the findings from the quantitative survey but also provided a platform for stakeholders to voice their opinions, share their experiences, and contribute to the discourse on

pre-primary education in Bangladesh. The qualitative data generated from these interviews and focus group discussions were instrumental in contextualizing the quantitative findings, ensuring a holistic and grounded understanding of the research topic.

3.3 Data Analysis

Quantitative Data Analysis

The quantitative data collected from the surveys were analyzed using statistical software. Descriptive statistics were employed to summarize the data, while inferential statistics were used to explore relationships between variables and test hypotheses.

Qualitative Data Analysis

The qualitative data from interviews and focus group discussions were transcribed verbatim and subjected to thematic analysis. This process involved coding the data, identifying patterns and themes, and interpreting the findings in relation to the research questions and objectives.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval was obtained from the relevant institutional review board before commencing the study. Informed consent was sought from all participants, ensuring they were aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and their rights as participants. Confidentiality and anonymity of the participants were maintained throughout the study.

Limitations

The study acknowledges certain limitations, including potential biases in self-reported data, the influence of social desirability on participants' responses, and the limitations inherent in the sample size and sampling method. These limitations were mitigated through triangulation of data sources, careful design of the data collection instruments, and transparency in reporting the study's findings and implications.

4 Result Analysis

4.1 Quantitative Analysis

The survey responses captures a snapshot of the current sentiment among education professionals in Bangladesh regarding the implementation of public policy in the pre-primary education sector. The following analysis will dissect these sentiments in detail, juxtaposing various factors such as role, experience, and specific opinions on policy and regulatory matters. The overwhelming majority of the survey's respondents are Teachers (78.12%), highlighting their frontline perspective in the pre-primary education sector. This is followed by Headteachers or Principals, comprising nearly a fifth of the sample (19.94%). The perspectives of Parents (1.79%) and Policymakers (0.15%) are notably underrepresented, which might skew the data towards the experiences and opinions of on-the-ground educational staff.

Figure 1: Awareness Regarding Government Planning

Figure 2: Awareness vs. Experience

Figure 3: Awareness vs. Infrastructure Resources

Figure 4: Challenges in Pre-Primary Education

Figure 5: Experience vs Infrastructure Resources

Figure 6: Experience vs Policy Effectiveness

Figure 7: Adequacy of Infrastructure and Resources

When considering the years of experience, the distribution is almost evenly split between those with 6-10

years (50.73%) and those with 11-20 years (49.27%) of service. This near-equal division offers a balanced view of the mid- to long-term experience in the sector, providing a solid foundation for assessing the effectiveness of policy over time. Awareness of government plans for pre-primary education is nearly ubiquitous among respondents, with an astounding 99.48% indicating familiarity with the initiative to introduce a two-year pre-primary education program by 2024. This high level of awareness contrasts sharply with the unanimous opinion on policy effectiveness—every respondent (100%) expressed the belief that current public policies are not effectively supporting the expansion and improvement of pre-primary education. This dichotomy between awareness and approval ratings underscores a critical gap between policy dissemination and policy reception or satisfaction.

The split in opinion regarding the effectiveness of communication about government decisions—50.58% positive and 49.42% negative—paints a picture of a sector divided on the clarity and efficacy of policy communication. This near-even split suggests that while some stakeholders feel adequately informed, a significant portion perceives a lack of effective communication, which could impact the overall reception of and engagement with these policies. In stark contrast to the divided opinions on communication, there is a clear consensus on the necessity of a regulatory framework, with 100% agreement among respondents. This unanimous perspective may reflect a collective recognition of the critical role that regulation plays in ensuring quality, particularly given the dominance of private institutions in the sector.

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The convergence of unanimous opinions on the insufficiency of budget allocation and the necessity of a regulatory framework with the split opinions on communication effectiveness reveals a complex landscape of stakeholder sentiment. It suggests that while there is a clear understanding of the sector's needs, there is less confidence in the government's current approach to meeting these needs. The survey data also indicate a sector that is deeply engaged yet critically reflective of the trajectory of public policy. The shared concerns over budgetary and regulatory adequacy, combined with the critical perception of policy effectiveness, signal a pressing need for policy reform and realignment with stakeholder expectations and the realities of the education sector.

4.2 Qualitative Analysis

While the quantitative data revealed clear trends in stakeholder opinions regarding government policies, regulatory frameworks, and budget allocations, the qualitative responses offered deeper insights into the reasons behind these opinions. Respondents provided narrative feedback that highlighted several key themes.

- **Theme 1: Policy Transparency and Clarity** Many educators expressed a desire for greater transparency in the policy-making process. They noted that while they were aware of the government's plans, the lack of detail and clarity in communication led to confusion and skepticism about the policies' practicality. Teachers shared anecdotes of policy announcements that were either too vague or too abrupt, leading to challenges in curriculum planning and classroom implementation.
- **Theme 2: Resource Constraints** A recurring theme in the qualitative data was the concern over resource constraints. Respondents pointed out that the lack of physical infrastructure, learning materials, and trained personnel were major barriers to implementing pre-primary policies effectively. This was particularly poignant in the context of the unanimous quantitative finding that current budget allocations are insufficient.
- **Theme 3: Regulatory Framework for Quality Assurance** Respondents also elaborated on the need for a regulatory framework, emphasizing that without enforceable standards, the quality of education varied significantly. Many educators called for more robust oversight and support systems to ensure that regardless of whether an institution was public or private, it could deliver a high standard of education.
- **Theme 4: Financial Commitment to Education** The qualitative data echoed the quantitative findings on budget sufficiency, with many stakeholders highlighting the gap between policy aspirations and financial realities. There was a clear call for increased investment in pre-primary education to provide a more equitable start for all children.

5 Discussion

The findings of this study into Bangladesh's pre-primary education policy implementation present a dichotomy between stakeholder awareness and perceived policy effectiveness. Despite the near-universal awareness of the government's plan to introduce a two-year pre-primary education by 2024, there is a unanimous view among respondents that current policies are not effectively supporting the sector's expansion or improvement. This unanimity may stem from a perceived disconnect between policy intention and practical execution. The data suggest that stakeholders, while informed, do not see the translation of policy into tangible benefits for pre-primary education. This could be attributed to various factors, such as inadequate infrastructure, insufficient teacher training, or a lack of pedagogical resources, which are not uncommon in developing countries' educational reforms.

The split in opinions on communication effectiveness, with approximately half of the respondents on either side, indicates a potential area for improvement. Effective communication is crucial for the successful implementation of any public policy. It is a conduit not just for conveying information but also for garnering support and facilitating the practical application of policy measures. The divided opinion here suggests that while some educational professionals feel adequately informed about policy changes, others are left wanting more clarity and consistency in communication. This divide may contribute to the overall dissatisfaction with policy effectiveness, as stakeholders who feel uninformed are less likely to view policies favorably. The resounding consensus on the necessity of a regulatory framework and the sufficiency of the current budget allocation represents a critical appraisal of the sector's needs. Stakeholders across the board see regulation as essential to maintaining quality education in the face of private sector dominance. This viewpoint underscores the sector's desire for equity and standardization in pre-primary education, which stakeholders believe can only be achieved through comprehensive regulation. Similarly, the unanimous opinion that the current budget allocation is insufficient suggests that stakeholders are acutely aware of the financial underpinnings required for effective policy implementation. Financial constraints are often a significant barrier to the realization of educational policies, particularly in the context of developing nations where competing needs and limited resources must be balanced.

6 Conclusion

The survey results provide a revealing glimpse into the attitudes and perceptions of professionals involved in Bangladesh's pre-primary education sector. The data indicate a strong desire for more effective public policies that are not only well-communicated but also well-funded and properly regulated. The findings suggest that achieving the government's goals for pre-primary education by 2024 will likely require a concerted effort to bridge the gap between policy formulation and its practical application on the ground. The clear demand for a regulatory framework and adequate budget allocation also points to a broader issue of trust in public sector management of education. Without belief in the government's commitment to and capacity for implementing these policies, stakeholder support may wane, which could jeopardize the success of these initiatives. This research highlights the need for a multi-faceted approach to policy implementation—one that addresses financial, regulatory, and communicative aspects of policy. It is recommended that policymakers Engage in more effective, clear, and consistent communication with all stakeholders to ensure that policy changes are understood and that feedback is incorporated into policy development. Re-evaluate the budgetary allocations to the pre-primary education sector to ensure that financial resources are not a limiting factor in the execution of these policies. Establish a regulatory framework that sets standards, ensures quality, and promotes fair practices across both public and private pre-primary education institutions. Finally, this study serves as a call to action for policymakers to consider the voices of those at the front lines of education. By aligning policy objectives with the practical realities and needs of pre-primary education professionals, there is an opportunity to foster a more robust, equitable, and effective educational environment for the youngest learners in Bangladesh. The conclusions drawn from this study are not without limitations. The underrepresentation of parents and policymakers in the respondent pool suggests that further research should aim to capture a broader range of perspectives. Additionally, the unanimous responses on several key issues may point to underlying systemic challenges that require in-depth qualitative research to fully understand and address.

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